

**De-Domesticating Sustainability:
Renewing the Transformative Imagination through Science–Church Collaboration
(First Draft version)**

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Introduction: Why “Dousing the Flames” Won’t Save Our Common Home

Emissions growth may be slowing and solar costs have plunged—but this is no time for complacency. The real challenge is steering change before climate tipping points and techno-optimism lock us into a self-defeating path.

A decade after *Laudato Si'*, the picture is mixed. Yes, the [rate of increase in global emissions has eased](#). But any sense of progress is precarious: it depends on us not crossing looming climate tipping points that could unleash destabilizing, potentially runaway change. And yes, [the price of solar has plummeted](#) since the encyclical—yet it is misleading to infer that we can simply swap fossil fuels for solar and declare “problem solved”.

The deeper story is metabolic. The global economy is undergoing a vast metabolic transition—a reconfiguration of how energy and materials flow through society. As Richard Heinberg has warned back in 2007 under the banner of “[peak everything](#)”, constraints across energy, minerals, land and water are converging. In his book [More and More and More. An All-Consuming History of Energy](#), Jean-Baptiste Fressoz goes further, arguing that the very notion of a clean “energy transition” is historically counterfactual: new energy sources have typically been additive, not substitutive, expanding total throughput rather than replacing the old. Taken together, these perspectives caution against the tempting narrative that the climate—and the broader ecological debacle—is on a straightforward path to resolution.

This is not the time to sigh in relief. With AI futures shaking our social and economic imagination to the core, the moment demands—but is arguably also ripe for—far-reaching social-ecological transformations; changes capable of building resilience against the tsunami we see approaching, while also mitigating its force as much as possible. As Bill McKibben told me in an impromptu interview at Castel Gandolfo during the [Raising Hope conference](#) last October, in commemoration of the 10th anniversary of *Laudato si'*: “When your house is on fire, you don’t discuss ideas of how to reform the house; you put off the fire”. The problem with the analogy is that, in our ecological reality, putting out the fire without reforming the house can entrench the very conditions that spread the flames—expanding the energy-material footprint while we apply foam to the hotspots. It is a self-defeating strategy. *Laudato Si'* invites a different posture: to “care for our common home” by pairing emergency response with structural redesign. The story only ends well if we quench the fire and re-build in ways that stop the flames from reclaiming the house—the only home we have or ever will have, notwithstanding delusional space-colonization fantasies. My argument is simple yet unsettling: that this requires reopening our narrowed socio-political discourse—going from defense from the unwanted impacts of AI and ecological degradation into an offensive redesign of our social-economic arrangements. This piece offers a deliberately provocative lens: What happens when sustainability science engages with an unlikely interlocutor, namely the Church? In this light, the “reciprocal irritation” between science and

faith traditions might just reopen pathways foreclosed by technocratic thinking and its far-right drifts—pathways that resonate with the spirit of *Laudato Si'*. Could this underexplored interface hold clues for the transformation we so urgently need?

This article develops its argument in three steps.

First, I revisit Pope Francis' landmark encyclical *Laudato Si'*—hailed by liberation theologian Leonardo Boff as the “[Magna Carta of integral ecology](#)”—and examine its socio-political significance against the backdrop of the mixed global reactions it has sparked over the past decade.

Second, I turn to what I see as the deeper problem behind today's sustainability impasse: not merely a governance deadlock, but a deadlocked sociological and political imagination. Despite some encouraging signals—slowing emissions growth, plunging solar costs—these trends risk creating a false sense of progress by obscuring structural realities: the metabolic scale of the global economy, resource constraints, and the historically misleading notion of a clean “energy transition”. This narrowing of discourse—about both the roots of “non-sustainability” and the pathways out of it—has become a key obstacle to transformative change.

Finally, I explore the mutual roles that sustainability science and the Church could play in reopening this discursive space. Drawing on insights from both domains, I outline what science might learn from the Church, and what the Church might learn from science, as they navigate the shared challenge of steering social-ecological transformation. This proposal aligns with the post-secular turn in social theory (Habermas, Joas, Casanova), which calls for dialogical engagement between secular and religious actors in shaping public reason. Sustainability governance, I argue, is a paradigmatic case where such engagement is not optional but necessary.

The article closes with an outlook on the future role of these two institutions—not as unlikely partners, but as complementary actors in the evolving landscape of sustainability governance.

Point One: *Laudato Si'*, the Magna Carta of Integral Ecology

When Pope Francis published his second encyclical, [Laudato Si': On Care for Our Common Home](#), in 2015, the Church made an unequivocal commitment to join the ecological conversion of our world as an institutional actor. The document appeared at a pivotal historical moment: after roughly half a century of environmental policy, mounting evidence of a global ecological crisis and its cascading consequences had yet to translate into commensurate political, economic, and social change.

The diagnosis of a “socio-ecological crisis”—a crisis triggered by the interplay of societal processes and environmental dynamics—has not only endured but become central to science, politics, business, and public discourse. This persistence underscores the continued relevance of *Laudato Si'*.

From a socio-political standpoint, the encyclical's content is not radically original. From an ecclesiastical-historical perspective, however, it is groundbreaking. It introduces a sharply critical tone into Church discourse on prevailing development trends, issuing an urgent call for a paradigm shift. Its significance has long outlived the confines of a single pontificate, establishing itself as a universal ethical framework with resonance far beyond the Church's immediate sphere of influence. The scientific community has echoed its core diagnosis—among others, Nobel laureate [Giorgio Parisi](#) and [climate scientist Johan Rockström](#) have voiced alignment. The Church, for its part, has expanded its intellectual references to challenge the technocratic paradigm, citing thinkers such as radical feminist scholar Donna Haraway. Meanwhile, [Marxist philosopher Slavoj Žižek](#) has gone so far as to identify the Church as one of the few remaining institutions capable of articulating a genuine critique of global capitalism.

However, the praise for Pope Francis was not unanimous. Opposition intensified dramatically with the Church's move toward structural critique. The conservative German newspaper *Frankfurter Allgemeine Zeitung* (FAZ) criticised the rejection of “green capitalism”. In its op-ed titled “[Poverty for all?](#)”, they accused the Church of romanticizing poverty. Similarly, the [Wall Street Journal \(WSJ\)](#) escalated its

rhetoric to suggest that the Vatican promotes "economic ruin". They attacked the calls for "Degrowth" (Diminution of Growth) and the Debt Cancellation of the Global South, viewing them as "ideas that keep them (the poor) poor". Meanwhile, lobbyists aligned with OPEC continue to argue that [fossil fuels are necessary for combating poverty](#). Political figures like Argentina's [libertarian President Javier Milei](#) and [Kevin Roberts of the Heritage Foundation](#) have framed climate action as a "socialist lie" to delegitimize the papal message.

Laudato Si' exposes the deeply normative character of current socio-political debates about the relationship between human society and non-human nature—normativity that is often masked by a pseudo-objective, technical, and economic veneer. The mixed reactions it has elicited over the years confirm that Pope Francis' encyclical was received globally, at the very least, as a sharp provocation to the status quo.

Point 2 My Central Thesis: The Narrowing of Discourse

In *Laudato Si'*, Pope Francis acknowledges that current human activity threatens the survival of humanity and countless other species by undermining the ecological foundations of life as we know it. The issues at stake—climate change, mass extinction, disruption of biogeochemical cycles, habitat destruction—are well documented. In this context, a historically unique alignment emerges: the Church's mission to advance God's kingdom now coincides with the imperative to safeguard God's creation as we understand it.

It is clear that humanity's failure to act is not due to ignorance, nor to a lack of data, facts, or technical capacity. As reiterated in successive scientific assessments, [including those of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change \(IPCC\)](#), the objective bases for action have long been established. This consensus is widely recognized; as [scientist Marta Rivera Ferre notes](#), the crisis stems not from a deficit of knowledge but from a structural failure to act on it.

Public discourse often reduces this failure to a "lack of political will", sometimes paired with claims about immature markets or unripe technologies. Ecclesiastical circles, by contrast, tend to frame the socio-ecological crisis as a spiritual rupture: due to its hubris, humanity has fractured its connection to God (the existential void), to nature (environmental destruction), to its fellow human beings (hyper-individualism and social inequality), and to itself (identity crisis). The inevitable result, in this view, is a "multiple crisis" of mutually reinforcing feedback loops across these spheres of existence.

It is not the intention of this article to refute any of these positions. There is a substantial body of evidence to support these theses, even if they are, at best, only partial and, at worst, misleading. Instead, my thesis is this: [the condition of "sustained unsustainability"](#), as [German sociologist Ingofur Blühdorn](#) terms it, is not primarily explained by these factors. Rather, the deeper problem lies in how we frame sustainability itself.

In other words, the core issue is a narrowing of socio-political discourse—both in diagnosing the roots of unsustainability and in imagining pathways out of it. This discursive closure slows, halts, or even reverses necessary social learning processes, as evidenced by the rise of right-wing populism and democratic backsliding.

Historically, sustainability began as a disruptive concept. Today, it has been domesticated into a consensual framework—one that permits only interpretations compatible with prevailing economic and cultural norms. In practice, this forecloses fundamental transformation, often described as "system change" or "paradigm shift" (terms echoed in *Laudato Si'*). The concept has been inverted: instead of subordinating our way of life to planetary boundaries, we now strive to subordinate creation to entrenched lifestyle expectations.

Against this backdrop, Pope Francis' call for a sufficiency perspective has gained traction within the academic community. This vision entails consciously curbing the expansive dynamics of modern

economies and lifestyles in favor of a future-proof society—one that is more solidaristic, inclusive, and life-affirming.

Point Three: The Role of Science and the Church in a Deadlocked Imagination

This section focuses on the mutual provocation that science and the Church can make to unlock the potential of both institutions in paving the way for global sustainability. The central question is how these two actors can help revitalize the sustainability discourse, restoring its transformative edge.

Provocations from Academia to the Church

Scientists worldwide are increasingly moving beyond their traditional role as neutral knowledge producers to engage directly with civil society in advocating for effective climate protection measures. This shift signals the scientific community's rejection of the "deficit model"—the idea that merely providing data will compel political action. This new stance has become strikingly visible: in Spain, [scientist Fernando Valladares faced criminal prosecution](#) not for falsifying data, but for civil disobedience, highlighting the moral urgency that now supersedes professional caution. The spectacle of scientists being penalized for calling attention to the emergency underscores the depth of the political failure. This moral escalation reached a new intensity in Germany, where a group of senior [climate researchers, out of sheer desperation, undertook a hunger strike in Berlin](#), publicly appealing to leaders to heed scientific warnings. Yet beyond lobbying and protest, a growing number of scientists recognize that social-ecological transformation demands more than pressure—it requires a recomposition of the sociopolitical substrate of modern societies. Only then can politics gain the legitimacy to implement measures that often contradict prevailing social norms—such as consumer freedom at the individual level or free trade at the structural level.

If scientific data and facts, even amplified by protest or civil disobedience, are insufficient to trigger the necessary cultural and political change, how can transformation be induced? Within this apparent paralysis lies an argument: the Church could make a decisive contribution on the world stage in the 21st century.

Historically, the Church has often served as a moral compass, encouraging temperance and restraint. Today, responsibility has shifted from political institutions to individuals—consumers, citizens, educators—who are compelled to reconcile environmental stewardship with the relentless acceleration of economic growth. In a social order driven by structural compulsion toward escalation, the individual is, as sociologist [Elizabeth Shove puts it, “imprisoned in the cage of unsustainability”](#). Consequently, moral appeals, rational persuasion, or utilitarian incentives are inadequate to induce comprehensive social transformation.

The question, then, is this: what meaningful role can the Church play beyond that of a moral advisor? Séverine Deneulin, [Director of International Development at the Laudato Si' Research Institute from Oxford University](#), contends that the Church's most significant contribution lies in challenging and transforming the prevailing narrative of global sustainable development. Currently, this narrative equates sustainable development with "green growth, net-zero [emissions], etc.—allowing us to continue with *business as usual* rather than making the changes that would truly address the problems with current development models". Deneulin highlights the contradictions embedded in this approach. Take the transition to electric vehicles: it has driven soaring demand for rare earth elements such as copper, cobalt, and lithium, fueling new waves of mining. Historically, mining has been associated with land disputes, human rights violations, water scarcity, and encroachment on Indigenous territories—particularly in Africa and Latin America. These concerns have prompted strong reactions from Catholic Episcopal Conferences across the Global South. In their [recent message to the UN ahead of COP30](#), they condemned “mining in the name of the energy transition” and “energy monoculture”, warning that

these practices “sacrifice communities and ecosystems” and violate human rights under the guise of false sustainability.

In light of the ineffectiveness of these so-called “green solutions” (such as electric cars) and the injustices they often engender—or at least exacerbate—, Deneulin argues that the Church’s role is twofold: to expose these hidden connections and to offer an alternative narrative of development, one rooted in solidarity and both personal and structural ecological conversion.

In other words, the Church could evolve into a global network of social innovation labs, where sustainability is not only modeled at a local scale but becomes the nucleus of a new social practice. With its unique combination of global reach and deep local presence, the Church is well positioned to help trigger so-called “social tipping points”. Put simply, this means gaining a critical mass for the necessary cultural and social change.

[John Milloy, director of the Centre for Public Ethics at Martin Luther University College in Canada, agrees.](#) “As Laudato Si’ reminds us”, says Milloy, “if all Catholics in Canada were not only to call for action on climate change, but also to support and implement the necessary lifestyle changes, this would bring about a fundamental change”. Yet this raises a crucial question: where will the guidelines for alternative conceptions of the good life—those that can underpin such lifestyle changes— come from? Markus Vogt, professor of Christian Social Ethics at LMU Munich, offers a starting point: [“Sustainability challenges the fixation of cultural notions of the good life on purely economic goals”](#). In [Why the Church? \(2024\)](#), [Hans Joas](#)—one of the leading voices in post-secular theory— pushes this further, portraying the Church not as a moralizing institution but as a powerhouse of cultural renewal, a communal space for cultivating human flourishing.

This perspective also intersects with institutional self-interest. Given the apparent inability of other global actors to catalyze a fundamental cultural shift toward a socioecological transformation, the universal Church faces a unique opportunity: to contribute decisively to the preservation of God’s creation. In doing so, it could also reclaim its waning social legitimacy and fulfill its transcendent mission: advancing the unfolding of God’s kingdom in the 21st century.

Laudato Si’ provides the mandate for this. But what practical knowledge does the Church need to implement a program of sufficiency-oriented cultural change, consistently and productively?

As the final point of this article, I will share some reflections on suggestions from the Church to science, before concluding with an outlook on the future role of both institutions.

Provocations from the Church to Academia

In my view, there are at least three distinct types of knowledge upon which the Church can draw to effectively unfold its role as a sustainability agent. Yet the academic sphere is currently over-invested in the first two—where transformative potential has largely peaked—and pays too little attention to the third.

The first type is data and facts. One of Laudato Si’’s most significant achievements—rightly praised—is its effort to resolve the historically fraught tension between science and faith. Pope Francis deliberately anchors his social critique and profession of faith in the latest scientific findings, thereby preempting any claim that his message of hope is detached from a sober, grounded analysis of reality. This same acknowledgment of scientific foundations underpins numerous ecclesial initiatives inspired by Laudato Si’’, including the Laudato Si’ Movement, the Economy of Francesco, and territorial networks such as REPAM (Red Eclesial Panamazónica) in the Amazon. The scientific groundwork underpins the political relevance of these initiatives, both at the territorial level—REPAM’s self-given mission, for example, is to protect life in the Amazon, resisting the expansion of extractive frontiers—and at the global level, where the Ecclesial Networks Alliance for an Integral Ecology (ENA) groups the various kindred catholic initiatives seeking to move beyond observation and directly influence negotiations at global sustainability summits, such as the latest climate COP30 in Belem, Brazil. In

doing so, the Church positions itself as a key actor in the geopolitics of sustainability, pushing global climate solutions to address systemic injustices and extractivism.

Yet, as (social) science itself demonstrates—and as argued here—data and facts alone are not the cornerstones of cultural change. Identity markers, narrative plausibility, and group dynamics play a far greater role. Moreover, the positivist attitude that seeks to grasp reality solely through quantification is problematic: it renders invisible everything that cannot be measured. This exclusion is particularly troubling in the context of the ecological crisis, where both *known unknowns* and *unknown unknowns* largely shape the terrain—and neither can be adequately quantified.

The second type is philosophical and theological knowledge. In my view, the Church currently pursues this type of knowledge even to an excessive degree. Fundamental theological impulses often yield insights that, while profound, have a low action-orientative value for the Church's own ecological conversion. Current eco-theological discourse is dominated by questions such as whether contemporary theology is overly anthropocentric, or what Christians' precise responsibility toward Creation entails. These debates may represent groundbreaking innovations in religious thought, but they offer little strategic guidance for institutional action.

This approach is further problematic because it says too little about how social change actually occurs. It risks romanticizing “ecological conversion” or reproducing outdated patterns of thought and action, where a “Christian label” is simply affixed to mainstream, yet largely ineffective, approaches that have dominated secular sustainability debates for decades, which typically emphasize individual-level gestures and downplays structural drivers of the social-ecological crisis. [As Markus Vogt emphasizes](#), ethical approaches often fail to weave empirical insights, socio-theoretical analysis, and normative argument into a coherent strategy for change. In the same vein, [Christian political philosopher Jonathan Chaplin warns against this](#), arguing that true conversion requires confronting the “specific pathologies of corporations, markets, consumption patterns, and governmental actions” that perpetuate ecological breakdown. This confrontation is essential because the crisis is fundamentally fueled by the illusion of unlimited economic growth—a principle deeply embedded in the dominant techno-economic paradigm. The “re-enchantment” of the world will not succeed unless these structural foundations of expansive modernity are squarely addressed.

This brings us to the third and final type of knowledge that could significantly strengthen the Church's role as a sustainability agent: a much closer integration of action theory and social theory (and, crucially, not limited to like-minded approaches) in favor of a clearer and more productive action orientation for the Church.

This presupposes, among other things, not only the Church's commitment to open dialogue with the full spectrum of social theory but also a willingness to critically interrogate its own normative assumptions. In light of the glaring shortcomings of global sustainability governance over the past 50 years—and the insights emerging from contemporary social theory—it becomes necessary to problematize and potentially redefine certain political-philosophical premises deeply embedded in Catholic Social Teaching (CST). These include historically contingent assumptions about the nature and social role of capital, labor, and their interdependence, which are rooted in the thermo-industrial revolution of the late 19th and 20th centuries. That these foundations are often taken for granted, obscuring their radical historical contingency, is increasingly problematic in the face of sustainability challenges. Worse still, they risk being rendered obsolete—perhaps abruptly—by developments such as (runaway?) AI fundamentally reshaping socio-economic configurations, which cannot be adequately confronted by simply invoking moral principles rooted in a radically different techno-economic context. In such a scenario, these assumptions could soon appear not only inadequate but even laughable, unless they are seriously revised and adapted.

Consequently, the socio-political function of the Church should not be—at least not primarily—that of a “lobbyist with (arguably) above-average moral credibility”, whose role is limited to reminding

political decision-makers of their responsibilities. Rather than relying exclusively on the moral integrity or rational decision-making of stakeholders—or on its own persuasive capacity—the Church must proactively engage in cultural transformation by developing a more advanced and impartial understanding of the mechanisms that enable social-economic change towards sustainability.

This guiding participation in cultural change involves challenging discursive one-sidedness, co-designing new social practices oriented toward sufficiency—that is, practices and cultural norms aimed at reducing resource use, consumption, and pollution, as opposed to sustainability strategies that rely solely on efficiency or consistency—and forging strategic alliances with non-church actors committed to mobilizing both the faithful and their non-Christian peers for what might be called a “Sufficiency Revolution”. The interplay among these approaches—discursive pluralization, practice prototyping, and alliance-building—creates the conditions for norm cascades and social tipping points, the kind of dynamic that, to quote John Milloy again, can “bring about a fundamental change”.

To summarize: although data and facts and fundamental theological impulses remain significant resources that science provides to the Church—resources that are already abundant and/or have relatively low action-orientation value—it is this third, hitherto neglected form of knowledge that is ultimately decisive for activating the Church’s transformative potential. This form of knowledge links diverse, intertwined, and tension-filled action-theoretical and social-theoretical perspectives to diagnose and re-design the actual mechanisms of change—norms, institutions, incentives, power, and narratives. Consequently, sustainability science and the Church must reconsider their respective roles at the interface and adjust priorities accordingly: moving from informing and exhorting to co-producing culturally embedded transformation.

Lastly: The science–Church interface proposed here is not a one-off experiment but sits squarely within the broader theoretical horizon of post-secularism. This perspective, as developed by thinkers like Habermas, Joas, and Casanova, insists that modern societies cannot afford to exclude religious traditions from public reasoning. In fact, the dialogical engagement between scientific and faith-based actors for sustainability transformation, not only broadens the interpretative space but also offers a testing ground for the practical relevance of post-secularism in addressing planetary crises.

Outlook

In his [Eleventh Thesis on Feuerbach, Karl Marx](#) famously wrote that philosophers have only interpreted the world, whereas the real challenge is to change it. Yet in the face of global disruptions—climate breakdown, mass extinction, and now the destabilizing implications of AI—we might argue, *contrario sensu*, that our techno-economic systems have changed the world too quickly and too unreflectively. To reshape it sustainably, we must first recover the capacity to reinterpret it.

This task begins with broadening the interpretative space, and, through that, reshaping social practice. Here, the role of both science and the Church is pivotal. The narrowing of the discursive space has not occurred by accident: it reflects not only the power of dominant actors to shape narratives but also the weight of historical path-dependency, which makes certain framings appear inevitable. When well-meaning actors accept these narratives as given, they acquire the force of a self-fulfilling prophecy. Breaking this cycle requires institutions capable of reopening discursive alternatives and modeling them in practice.

For this reason, the Church’s role cannot be reduced to lobbying or moral exhortation. It must embrace a form of “creative destruction”, to borrow and resignify Joseph Schumpeter’s metaphor. In this context, the primary agents of creative destruction should not be market forces but knowledge- and faith-driven institutions, operating on the premise articulated by Pope Francis:

“Every effort to protect and improve our world entails profound changes in lifestyles, models of production and consumption, and the established structures of power which today govern societies”.

It is only through the incorporation of previously marginalized actors, methodologies, and discourses that we can establish a foundation for a more balanced evaluation of potential solutions. This inclusive process is vital for tapping into the vast reservoir of ontological, epistemological, and practice-based approaches that humanity has accumulated throughout its millennia-long history. In this urgent hour, these approaches are imperative if humanity is to survive the fatal consequences of its own hubris. Ten years on, the central provocation of *Laudato Si'* —its urgent call for a paradigm shift— remains powerfully relevant. Its enduring value lies not only in its spots-on diagnosis but in its mandate for both the Church and the scientific community to become critical agents of cultural transformation, capable of transcending the political and discursive deadlock that has stalled meaningful action. This means moving beyond lobbying and technocratic fixes toward co-producing sufficiency-oriented social practices and narratives that can trigger social tipping points and steer humanity toward a livable future.